

OBSERVING AND EVALUATING THE CHARACTERISTICS AND BEHAVIOR OF LEADERS BY EMPLOYEES

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Abstract. *The article is aimed at monitoring and assessing the characteristic features and behavior of leaders by employees of a specialized educational institution. Also, these features of leaders were classified separately. Keywords: management of an educational institution, approach to managing the development of a specialized educational institution, characteristics of the leader, behavior, tasks, methods.*

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It is not enough to hold a leadership position to be a leader. The skills and qualities of a leader are determined by the ability to unite and inspire other people to implement an idea or project¹.

In a broad sense, control is the regulation of the state of any system to achieve a clearly defined result. Ultimately, personnel management has two main goals: organization (for example, in a boarding school: organizing the educational process) and satisfying the personal needs and interests of employees. They are called target functions within boarding school management:

- education and upbringing of children on the basis of a correctional approach, obeying the social order to prepare them for life (organizational, pedagogical and financial-economic activities that contribute to ensuring an optimal and effective educational process);

- social or socio-psychological - regulating the emotional state of the community; aimed at satisfying the teachers and educators themselves, their interests, material and spiritual needs and requirements (creating comfortable work and communication conditions at work, encouraging a favorable microclimate, creative activity and effective work). An important aspect of the socio-psychological function within the school management, in general, includes the activity of organizing, uniting, activating (stimulating), improving, and developing the pedagogical team.

The ability to take responsibility at the right time and direct all efforts in the right direction to achieve goals is his main advantage at any stage of a leader's career. Even if the leader's professional path is just beginning, he should learn to demonstrate leadership skills as soon as possible. True leadership is sincerity, commitment to principles and professionalism, which can lead a leader to success in any area of life². Management will certainly notice an initiative and enthusiastic employee who is not afraid of challenges and is ready to take on additional responsibilities, which means that he can perform responsible tasks in a senior position.

We present below the evaluation questionnaire in the form of observation of the characteristic features and behavior of the leader, which shows the list of the main characteristics and behavioral options of the evaluators. A set of characteristics of how an employee performs his job, rated on a scale of importance, is evaluated in points.

As a result of this leader's characteristics evaluation questionnaire, he gets a fair assessment of the level of his characteristic characteristics. The employees participating in this survey as evaluators should carefully study and understand each question and evaluate it on the basis of

fairness, without any external influences. The results of the survey show the lack of characteristics of the leader and the aspects that should be worked on in the future. From this, the leader draws a correct conclusion and sets future plans.

Employees participating in the survey are required to have certain knowledge about the characteristics of managers. In this regard, we introduce the following characteristics of leaders. Ability to solve problems. Experienced leaders understand well how to solve the problems that arise. They are able to see their essence, break down complex tasks into simple components, build processes and find working solutions.

Broad-mindedness. In order to easily overcome problems, one should not be afraid of new ideas, approaches or views, regardless of their source. Understanding that no one can know everything is an important quality for a leader, which helps to look at things more broadly and to look for solutions in different sources, traditions and cultures.

The ability to inspire. There is no need to openly or formally monitor the contributions of others to the overall project. You don't always have to be a manager to lead a team. Leaders are people who use the tools at their disposal to inspire and motivate others.

Intuition. A good leader should always trust his instincts. He learns from his own experience, and also listens to the opinions of others and the recommendations of his colleagues, who in turn inspire him.

Innovative views. This is the ability to look at things in a new way, to give a chance to an unusual idea, to listen carefully to all opinions and suggestions from different sources. It is also not afraid of experiments, willingness to make mistakes and try again. A true leader needs all the qualities usually found in creative people.

Kindness. The ability to maintain a friendly attitude without negative impressions helps to impress not only certain individuals, but also the entire team. Negative moments often accumulate in work teams and quickly "break" relationships. A good leader can find a way to overcome these challenges and focus on completing tasks or achieving goals for superior results.

Trust. Believe in yourself. As a leader, you can't know everything, but if you have the right attitude and don't have bias, it won't be difficult to find a solution. In addition, trust means the understanding that everyone thinks in their own way and the ability to learn from someone else's experience. Active work for results creates inner confidence, which is communicated to other people and inspires them.

Positive communication skills. To lead others, you need to share your plans and talk about the role of others in your ideas, plans or vision. If you want to express different concepts clearly and clearly and win over like-minded people, you can't do without working on improving your communication skills.

Ability to delegate authority. You can never do everything alone. And most people hate it when their every move is under scrutiny. The ability to delegate authority and recognize strengths is one of the most important skills of a leader, which allows you to inspire and motivate others, as well as use their qualities to achieve a common result.

Conscientiousness. Don't hide your intentions. Others need to notice not only your excellent communication skills, but also your commitment to principles, and understand that you will not offend them. Speak like yourself and don't try to take back words.

Identify. At every moment, the leader must clearly understand the final goal, the steps to achieve it, and the ways to overcome possible obstacles on the way.

Emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is an interpersonal communication skill that helps to successfully establish work and informal relationships in a team or with individuals. Learn to understand others on an emotional level and develop communication skills.

Persistence. It is not necessary to give up halfway in the realization of the goal. No matter how difficult or time-consuming the task, always remember how your efforts will pay off. The absolute mark of a true leader is the ability to overcome challenges and move forward in a dignified way, no matter what³.

Reliability. Strive to adhere to a set schedule, always be on time and complete tasks completely and on time. Convince others to believe in you.

Working on relationships. Always trying to figure out what other people's strengths (and weaknesses) are. Helping people develop strong traits to achieve alignment of action and more effective performance of tasks as relationships strengthen.

Strategic thinking. You need to know why you are doing something. Try to evaluate the appropriateness of a particular task and its importance for the overall goal. Learn how to properly use available resources to achieve the desired result. Analyze the different stages of the plan to understand their relationship³.

Organization. Correct timing, planning and reporting - all this is a good organization of the process, in which tasks are performed exactly on time.

Pedantry. "Acceptable (satisfaction)" is an unsatisfactory result for the leader. Strict adherence to certain requirements and rules set by society, taking into account all the little things. Showing oneself in accordance with the rules of etiquette in exposing the mistakes of other people. A calm, tidy, clear person who performs his tasks thoroughly and does not need external supervision.

Humility. It embodies such rare qualities as knowing one's identity, respecting others, humanity: sincerity, innocence, kindness, compassion.

Sincerity. It is easier to identify a person who is prone to insincere or empty conversations. The real leader is immediately visible. His sincere confidence in his words and deeds gives him away. This is a kind of natural attraction.

Think about how many of these qualities you already have and which ones you need to work on. Being a leader is the same skill as everyone else. It can be improved, developed and continuously improved.

A sample form for evaluating the characteristics and behavior of managers (excerpt)

Characteristic feature							
1	He does not wait for problems, he can foresee problems.						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
2	He can explain well						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
3	Values time						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always

4	He is easy to talk to						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
5	Becomes a leader when working in a group						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
6	Spends time on essential aspects of work						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
7	Calm and calm in solving problems						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
8	Hardworking, works hard						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
9	Updates are constantly being introduced.						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
10	Can separate employees according to the performance of the task.						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
11	Can motivate employees according to the performance of the task.						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
12	He listens to the opinions of others and the recommendations of his colleagues						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
13	Ability to delegate and recognize strengths						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
14	Loyal for the principles						
	Observing behavior						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
15	He comes to work six days a week						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always

16	On time at work place						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
17	If it is absent or late, it will be known in the office						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
18	In his absence, he finds a replacement.						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
19	Reports to the team in the prescribed manner.						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
20	He himself follows the procedures he requires.						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
21	Dealing with justice is its main principle						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
22	I respect as a leader						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always
23	I am afraid as a leader.						
	Almost never	0	1	2	3	4	almost always

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